

IMPACT OF PHACOEMULSIFICATION AND FEMTOSECOND LASER-ASSISTED CATARACT SURGERY ON INTRAOCULAR PRESSURE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Usama Elahi¹, Mubarka Arooj², Hafsa Majeed³, Hamna Quddoos Sadiq⁴, Tahira kalsoom⁵, Shah Fahad⁶

¹Optometrist, Layton Rahmatullah Benevolent Trust, Eye Hospital, Akora Khattak, Nowshera

²MSc Vision Sciences, University of Montreal, Canada

^{3, *4,5}The University of Lahore

⁶MS Rehabilitation Superior University Lahore

¹usama.learner@gmail.com, ²mubarka.arooj@umontreal.ca, ³haf93938900@gmail.com,

⁴hamnaquddoos@gmail.com, ⁵tahira.kalsoom@ahs.uol.edu.pk, ⁶fahad.learner@gmail.com

¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-6595-5188>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19481076>

Keywords

OP, Cataract, Healthy Subjects, Phacoemulsification, FLACS

Article History

Received: 13 February 2024

Accepted: 23 March 2024

Published: 08 April 2024

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Hamna Quddoos Sadiq

Abstract

Purpose: The relationship between IOP and Cataract surgery involves both long-term and immediate effects. Extracting the cloudy lens and replacing it with an artificial intraocular lens can cause a short-term increase in IOP immediately after the procedure due to fluid shift and the use of viscoelastic substances. Long-term cataract surgery often leads to a reduction in IOP, which is particularly beneficial for patients with conditions like glaucoma. For glaucoma patients, temporary OP spikes can pose risks, so surgeons follow techniques and medication to manage the pressure during and after surgery.

Objective: To compare the effects of Femtosecond laser-assisted cataract surgery (FLACS) and conventional Phacoemulsification cataract surgery on intraocular pressure after surgery in cataract patients.

Methodology. This comparative cross-sectional study reviewed 140 cataract patients who underwent FEMTOSECOD LASER-ASSISTED and PHACOEMULSIFICATION cataract surgery. The data was collected from both femto and phaco groups with all clinical and medical records by a self-made Performa after obtaining consent at UOL Teaching Hospital, Lahore, and Amanat Eye Hospital, Rawalpindi, from 30 July 2024 to Nov- 2024. An air puff tonometer was used to measure Pre-op and Post-op IOP. Post-op IOP was measured on the 1st and 3rd week.

Results. In the phaco and femto group, the mean difference of pre-op and post-op IOP measured was 1.95 ± 0.97 mmHg and 1.19 ± 2.60 mmHg, respectively ($p=0.309$). However, the Phaco group measures IOP 0.77 mmHg less than the femto group. In the femto group, the mean of Pre-Op and post-Op IOP at 1st and 2nd weeks was 16.08 ± 3.36 mmHg, 15.26 ± 3.13 mmHg and 14.13 ± 2.95 mmHg respectively ($p<0.001$). Likewise, in the phaco group, the mean of Pre-Op and post-Op IOP at 1st and 2nd week was 14.4 ± 3.146 mmHg, 13.7 ± 2.82 mmHg, and 13.21 ± 2.76 mmHg respectively ($p<0.001$). **Conclusion.** The study concluded that there is no significant difference between mean post-operative IOP in FLACS and

phacoemulsification postoperative IOP. However, in the phaco group, there is less increase of IOP recorded as compared to the femto group.

Conclusion. This study demonstrated, there was a significant change in intraocular pressure (IOP) before and after phacoemulsification 14.4 ± 3.146 mmHg, 13.7 ± 2.82 mmHg, and 13.21 ± 2.76 mmHg and FLACS 16.08 ± 3.36 mmHg, 15.26 ± 3.13 mmHg, and 14.13 ± 2.95 mmHg. The IOP slightly decreases after both surgical procedures. Statistically comparing the mean pre- and post-IOP values of both procedures shows no significant changes as the mean difference is 0.77 and $p = 0.309$ (Table 4).

INTRODUCTION:

Just like blood plasma, Aqueous humor is a transparent, water-like fluid in which protein concentration is low. It is present in front of the crystalline lens, residing within the posterior and anterior chamber of the eye, with a volume of 0.30 ml and a refractive index of 1.33. The aqueous humor is a fluid characterized by low viscosity, perpetually secreted, and absorbed within the eye, this delicate equilibrium between secretion and reabsorption plays a vital role in controlling the volume and pressure of the intraocular fluid ⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾. Thus, the equilibrium between the aqueous humor's production and outflow in the eye is the key factor that determines intraocular pressure ⁽³⁾. Located in the anterior portion of the pars plicata, nestled within the ciliary processes of the ciliary body, is the focal point to produce aqueous humor. This transparent fluid originates from the plasma within the ciliary processes and traverses into the posterior chamber. Diffusion, ultrafiltration, and secretion are the key mechanisms involved in transporting aqueous humour from these tissues ⁽⁴⁾.

The intraocular pressure changes during the day and night. Normal eyes experience a diurnal variation of 3 to 6 mmHg; glaucomatous eyes may experience an increase in this variation. Even though the production of aqueous humor is slower during the night, intraocular pressure may not drop ⁽⁵⁾.

The 24-hour IOP profiles of glaucoma patients may not resemble those of healthy people. Exercise may have an impact on IOP, according to some conflicting research (some positively and some negatively ⁽⁶⁾. Changes in intraocular pressure (IOP) in the consensual eye after unilateral glaucoma surgery have been documented; however, the research currently in publication is contradictory, with some studies indicating a decline in contralateral eye IOP and

others indicating an increase ⁽⁷⁾. Laser surgery has been a recognized technique in several medical specialties for a long time. Laser usage in medical facilities is also rising. The benefit of lasers is that they are less intrusive and can produce outcomes comparable to those of traditional surgery^{3, 4}. However, there is typically reduced post-operative edema and inflammation following laser surgery, indicating a high chance for recovery ⁽⁸⁾. The complicated illness known as pseudo-exfoliation syndrome (PXS) affects the visceral organs and the eye ⁽⁹⁾. In many tissues and organs, particularly the anterior components of the eye, it is characterized by the gradual development and buildup of aberrant fibrillar extracellular deposits. The PEX material is a glycoprotein-proteoglycan complex that is cross-linked, highly glycosylated, and resistant to enzymes. Glycoconjugates encircle a protein core to form it. One kind of secondary open-angle glaucoma that is very aggressive is exfoliative glaucoma. It is characterized by higher IOP levels, more significant IOP changes throughout the day, a higher risk of optic nerve injury, and a poorer response to treatment.

These factors all work together to hasten the onset of parametric involvement and optic neuropathy. In patients with PEX syndrome, a unique surgical technique known as "goniowash" is utilized in addition to cataract surgery to remove PEX debris and lower intraocular pressure. The procedure is a simple additional washout of the anterior chamber of the eye, TM, and ICA ⁽¹⁰⁾. 80% of eye procedures are cataract surgeries, and intraocular surgeries are one of the main causes of endothelial impairment. For cataract surgery, phacoemulsification is regarded as the gold standard ⁽¹¹⁾. IOP is lowered in phacoemulsification, but over the course of a long-term follow-up, this effect is reversed in

both healthy individuals and glaucoma patients. As a result, ongoing observation of IOP variation is required. For young patients and those with greater preoperative IOP, phacoemulsification by itself is a dependable method of controlling IOP⁽¹²⁾.

Recent advances in cataract surgery have included the use of femtosecond lasers for astigmatism correction, lens fragmentation, and continuous curvilinear capsulorhexis (CCC). Femtosecond lasers have precise CCC with a good intraocular lens (IOL) centration, little endothelium loss, and quick phacoemulsification times. Minimizing endothelial cell death during cataract surgery was one of the advantages of femtosecond laser-assisted cataract surgery (FLACS) over traditional techniques⁽¹³⁾. Femtosecond laser systems in cataract surgery can use real-time imaging technologies like anterior segment imaging or optical coherence tomography (OCT) to provide high-resolution images of the eye's structures. This can help create a precisely sized and centered capsulotomy, treat corneal astigmatism, and make clear corneal incisions and fragment lenticular material. Apart from its use in cataract surgery, femtosecond laser advancements in refractive surgery are many and constantly changing. These are mostly in the areas of Laser-Assisted in Situ Keratomileusis (LASIK) flap formation, Small Incision Lenticule Extraction (SMILE), and Penetrating Keratoplasty (PK)⁽¹⁴⁾. The development of femtosecond laser technology was spurred by the demonstrated great accuracy and reproducibility of femtosecond laser-assisted capsulotomy, which expanded the technology's role in replacing the traditional surgical processes of cataract surgery (as established by conventional phacoemulsification). As a result, the FLACS area of practice now includes corneal incisions and laser-assisted lens fragmentation, raising the prospect of improved surgical results⁽¹⁵⁾. Some healthy eyes experience an increase in intraocular pressure (IOP) following the FLACS laser operation, FLACS is associated with a later decrease in IOP. Like CPCS, FLACS lowers IOP, however it tends to be more noticeable in eyes with greater preoperative IOP. Patients with glaucoma should take this into account since eyes with

greater preoperative IOP are more likely to have their IOP elevated during FLACS⁽¹⁶⁾.

Over the past 20 years, the most popular technique has been cataract surgery using the phacoemulsification technique. When compared to the previous ECCE method, phacoemulsification offers numerous advantages, such as a smaller, safer incision, less postoperative astigmatism, and early refraction stabilization. The decrease in issues related to surgical wounds, like iris prolapse, is another benefit of this method⁽¹⁷⁾. The intricate machinery needed to separate the lens nucleus and remove it through the tiny incision may be a drawback of this procedure. To master the techniques, a cataract surgeon requires extensive training and experience. The procedure for modern phacoemulsification cataract removal is as follows. Topical anesthetics are injected into the conjunctival sac after the eyelids and lashes have been draped to separate them from the surgical field. The transparent cornea is cut through one large incision and two smaller ones. The anterior chamber is injected with viscoelastic. Next, a circular incision known as a capsulorhexis 99 is made; it ought to be central, curvilinear, and continuous. The process of hydro dissection makes it easier to rotate the nucleus and separates the cortex and nucleus from the capsule. The anterior chamber of the eye is where the phaco probe is inserted. With a frequency of about 40 000 Hz, or 40 000 oscillations per second, the probe produces a high-frequency moment of its tip. A probe is used to divide the nucleus into four quadrants before each is emulsified. Aspiration removes the lens cortex. Before the IOL (Intraocular Lens) insertion Ocular Lens), viscoelastic fills the capsule. Next, the IOL is placed inside the capsular bag; at this point, a specialized injector is used. Aspiration is used to extract viscoelastic from the anterior chamber. By injecting a salt solution into the corneal stroma, stromal hydration is achieved, sealing the incisions. Lastly, to avoid infection, a subconjunctival injection of steroids and antibiotics is administered⁽¹⁸⁾⁽¹⁹⁾⁽²⁰⁾.

Materials and Methodology: This cross-sectional analytical study reviewed 140 patients (70 patients per surgery) records of FLACS and PHACO cases at The Layton Rahmatullah

Benevolent Trust (LRBT) Lahore and Amanat Eye Hospital Rawalpindi from 30 July 2024 to Nov- 2024. Approval by the institutional ethics committee was obtained and the study was performed according to the hospital protocols. Informed consent was obtained before data collection from all subjects. This study was approved by the head of the ophthalmology department of the hospital. The patients were classified into two groups according to their operation methods. Inclusion criteria were symptomatic cataracts for which the patient desires surgery with age above 45 years. Exclusion criteria were unable to give consent for surgery and research and any other ocular disease than cataract. Only one eye of each patient was included in the study, and in cases of bilateral cataracts, the eye undergoing surgery first was included. Preoperatively, the medical histories of all patients were recorded. Intraocular pressure measurement was performed with an air-puff tonometer (Topcon

CT 80 computerized tonometer). Post-operative visits occur in 1st week and 3rd week of the surgery. A routine examination, including intraocular pressure (IOP), assessment, and notation of any complication. Continuous data is conveyed by mean ± standard deviation and categorical data by number (percentage). Comparison among FLACS and conventional groups was analyzed using SPSS 20. The level of significance was set at a P-value of less than 0.05 for all parameters.

Results and discussion

A total of 140 patients were included in this study, with 70 patients undergoing phacoemulsification and 70 patients undergoing femtosecond laser-assisted cataract surgery (FLACS). The gender distribution was equal across the overall sample, with 70 females (50%) and 70 males (50%) (see Table 1).

Table 1: Frequency table of gender distribution

Gender	N	Percent
Female	70	50%
Male	70	50%
Total	140	100%

The age distribution within both surgical groups showed slight variation between male and female patients. In the FLACS group, the mean age was 60.55 ± 9.08 years for females and 59.90 ± 7.26 years for males. In the

phacoemulsification group, the mean age was 61.46 ± 7.85 years for females and 60.42 ± 6.62 years for males (see Table 2). These results indicate that both groups were comparable in terms of demographic distribution.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of age

Type of surgery		N	imimage	imimage	Mean ± SD	
Age	FLACS	Female	29	43	78	60.55 ± 9.08
		Male	41	46	77	59.90 ± 7.26
	Phacoemulsification	Female	46	43	77	61.46 ± 7.85
		Male	24	48	76	60.42 ± 6.62

When assessing intraocular pressure (IOP) changes, the FLACS group demonstrated a gradual decline from a preoperative mean of 16.08 ± 3.36 mmHg to 15.26 ± 3.13 mmHg at

the first postoperative week and 14.13 ± 2.95 mmHg at the second postoperative week. This reduction was statistically significant (p < 0.001) (see Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of mean IOP between pre-operatives, post-operative 1st week, and post-operative 2nd

Week in FLACS Procedure

Group	N	Mean IOP	P value	Diff (pre IOP with Post - IOP1 ST Week)	Std. Dev	Diff(pre-IOP with Post-IOP 2 nd Week)	Std.Dev
Pre-IOP	70	16.0836 ± 3.356	<0.001	0.82171	0.828	1.9507	0.967
Post-IOP	70	15.2619 ± 3.137					
Post-IOP	70	14.1329 ± 2.953					

Similarly, in the phacoemulsification group, preoperative IOP averaged 14.4 ± 3.15 mmHg, which decreased to 13.7 ± 2.82 mmHg at the first postoperative week and further reduced to

13.21 ± 2.75 mmHg at the second postoperative week. This reduction was also statistically significant (p < 0.001) (see Table 4).

Table4: Comparison of mean pre-IOP with post-IOP of 1st and 2nd week in Phacoemulsification procedure

Group	N	Mean IOP	P value	Mean Diff pre-IOPwith (post-IOP 1 st Week) ± SD	Mean Diff pre-IOPwith (post-IOP 2 nd Week) ± SD
Pre-IOP	70	14.4 ±3.15	<0.001	0.7 ± 2.11	1.19 ± 2.6
Post-IOP 1st week	70	13.7 ± 2.8			
Post-IOP 2nd week	70	13.21 ± 2.75			

Direct comparison between the two surgical groups showed that the mean reduction in IOP was 1.95 ± 0.97 mmHg in the FLACS group and 1.19 ± 2.60 mmHg in the phacoemulsification group. The mean intergroup difference was 0.77

mmHg, which was not statistically significant (p = 0.309). Thus, both procedures demonstrated a mild decrease in IOP postoperatively, without a significant difference between them (see Table 5).

Table 5: Comparison of the mean difference between pre-operative IOP and post-IOP of FLACS and Phacoemulsification

	N	Mean ± SD	d.Error Mean	P value	Mean Diff.
Pre and post-IOP FLACS	70	1.95 ± 0.97	0.12	0.309	0.77
Pre and post-IOP Phaco	70	1.19 ± 2.60	0.31		

Discussion: This study evaluated and compared intraocular pressure (IOP) changes following Femtosecond Laser-Assisted Cataract Surgery (FLACS) and conventional phacoemulsification (19). Our findings demonstrate a consistent postoperative reduction in IOP across both surgical techniques, with no statistically

significant difference between them (mean difference: 0.77 mmHg; p = 0.309). In the FLACS group, mean IOP decreased from 16.08 ± 3.36 mmHg preoperatively to 15.26 ± 3.13 mmHg at week 1 and 14.13 ± 2.95 mmHg at week 2 (p < 0.001). Similarly, in the phacoemulsification group, IOP declined from

14.4 ± 3.15 mmHg preoperatively to 13.7 ± 2.82 mmHg at week 1 and 13.21 ± 2.76 mmHg at week 2 ($p < 0.001$) (16). These results align with previous studies reporting a modest early postoperative reduction in IOP after cataract surgery, with the greatest benefit observed in eyes with higher baseline IOP. Although a transient IOP rise is commonly associated with FLACS due to suction ring application, our study observed an overall decreasing trend by the second postoperative week. This finding is consistent with Wang et al., who reported significant suction-induced IOP spikes during FLACS, followed by postoperative normalization (15). Similarly, Zamani et al. demonstrated that both phacoemulsification and FLACS result in comparable IOP reductions over time, particularly in eyes with elevated preoperative pressure. The slightly greater mean IOP reduction in the phacoemulsification group (1.19 ± 2.60 mmHg) compared to FLACS (1.95 ± 0.97 mmHg) was not statistically significant, suggesting that surgical technique alone does not play a decisive role in long-term IOP control. Factors such as preoperative IOP, anterior chamber depth, and patient comorbidities may exert greater influence. Our findings support the safety of both techniques in terms of IOP stability and reinforce the growing evidence that cataract extraction—regardless of method—can provide a mild IOP-lowering effect in the early postoperative period. However, long-term studies with extended follow-up are needed to clarify whether this effect persists and to determine the optimal surgical approach for patients with coexisting ocular hypertension or glaucoma.

Conclusion: According to the study conducted, there was a significant change in intraocular pressure (IOP) before and after phacoemulsification 14.4 ± 3.146 mmHg, 13.7 ± 2.82 mmHg, and 13.21 ± 2.76 mmHg and FLACS 16.08 ± 3.36 mmHg, 15.26 ± 3.13 mmHg, and 14.13 ± 2.95 mmHg. The IOP slightly decreases after both surgical procedures. Statistically comparing the mean pre- and post-IOP values of both procedures, shows no significant changes as the mean difference is 0.77 and $p = 0.309$ (table 5).

REFERENCES:

- Sunderland DK, Sapra A. Physiology, Aqueous Humor Circulation. Stat Pearls. Treasure Island (FL) ineligible companies. Disclosure: Amit Sapra declares no relevant financial relationships with ineligible companies.: Stat Pearls Publishing
- Civan MM, Anthony. The ins and outs of aqueous humor secretion. 2004 Mar 1;78(3):625-31.
- Copyright © 2024, Stat Pearls Publishing LLC.; 2024.
- Levin LA, Nilsson SFE, Hoeve JV, Wu S, Kaufman PL, Alm A. Adler's Physiology of the Eye: Expert Consult - Online and Print: Elsevier Health Sciences; 2011.
- Chapter 6 - Aqueous and Vitreous Humors. 2012:109-22.
- Li M, Wang M, Guo W, Wang J, Sun X. The effect of caffeine on intraocular pressure: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol. 2011;249(3):435-42.
- Thornit DN, Sander B, la Cour M, Lund-Andersen H. The effects of peroral glycerol on plasma osmolarity in diabetic patients and healthy individuals. Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol. 2009;105(5):289-93.
- Dada T, Verma S, Gagrani M, Bhartiya S, Chauhan N, Satpute K, et al. Ocular and Systemic Factors Associated with Glaucoma. J Curr Glaucoma Pract. 2022;16(3):179-91.
- Rajsrinivas D, Dubey S, Pegu J, Majumdar A. Consensual eye intra-ocular pressure rise following unilateral glaucoma surgery. Indian journal of ophthalmology. 2023 Mar; 71:873-9.
- Hohmann M, Kühn D, Ni D, Späth M, Ghosh A, Rohde M, et al. Relevant parameters for laser surgery of soft tissue. Scientific Reports. 2024 Jan;14.
- Panigrahi S, Mishra T, Mishra P. Study of clinical profile of pseudo-exfoliation syndrome and pseudo-exfoliation cataract in a tertiary health care hospital in western Odisha. International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research. 2024 Jul;26-9.

- Baek SU, Kwon S, Park IW, Suh W. Effect of Phacoemulsification on Intraocular Pressure in Healthy Subjects and Glaucoma Patients. *Journal of Korean Medical Science*. 2019;34(6).
- Vallée R, Meduri E, Vallée JN, Lallouette A, Haffane Z, Paillard A, et al. Predictive biomarkers of intra-ocular pressure decrease after cataract surgery associated with trabecular washout in patients with pseudoexfoliative glaucoma. *Scientific Reports*. 2024 Jun;14.
- Hasan M, Kajmina N, Begum H. A comparison of functional endothelial changes between phacoemulsification with PCIOL and manual small incision cataract surgery with PCIOL. *Mugda Medical College Journal*. 2024 Jul; 7:14-8.
- Chung H, Lee H, Park SY, Min C, Kim M, Kim J, et al. Intraocular pressure changes before and after a femtosecond laser procedure for cataract surgery. *Scientific Reports*. 2024 Apr;14.
- Mathalone N, BenShaul O, Podkovyrin O, Lux C, Geyer O. The Impact of Femtosecond Laser on Intraocular Pressure with Cataract Surgery in Healthy Eyes. *Journal of Glaucoma*. 9900;
- Suh R, deBroff B. Femtosecond laser applications in ophthalmic surgery. *Medical Research Archives*. 2023 Oct;11.
- Salgado R, Torres P, Marinho A. Update on femtosecond laser-assisted cataract surgery: A review. *Clinical Ophthalmology*. 2024 Feb; 18:459-72.
- Loesel F, Tien AC, Backus S, Murnane M, Kurtz R, Sayegh S, et al. Effect of reduction of laser pulse width from 100 ps to 20 fs on the plasma-mediated ablation of hard and soft tissue. *Proc SPIE*. 1999 Jan;3565.
- Latz C, Asshauer T, Rathjen C, Mirshahi A. Femtosecond-Laser Assisted Surgery of the Eye: Overview and Impact of the Low-Energy Concept. *Micromachines*. 2021 Jan 24;12(2):122.